

We are running this survey to evaluate the effectiveness of an online simulation on the Gastrointestinal Smooth Muscle Activity. Your participation in this survey is voluntary, there are no marks associated with participation and you are free to decline from participation or withdraw at any time.

Please answer all questions to the best of your knowledge.

1. Which lectures did you attend or watch on gut physiology?

Check all that apply.

- Gut 1 on Monday 9/5 at 5pm
- Gut 2 on Tuesday 10/5 at 9am
- Gut 3 on Thursday 12/5 at 5pm

2. How long did you spend reading the notes in your practical manual?

Mark only one option.

- I didn't read them.
- Less than 10 minutes.
- Between 10 and 20 minutes.
- More than 20 minutes.

3. When did you go through the simulation?

Mark only one option.

- I didn't look at the simulation.
- Immediately before coming to the practical.
- The day before the practical.
- More than one day before the practical.

4. How long did you spend in total going through the simulation?

Mark only one option.

- I didn't look at the simulation.
- Less than 10 minutes.
- Between 10 and 20 minutes.
- More than 20 minutes.

5. For the experimental recording shown below, electrical stimulation of the nerves:

- Increased the contraction amplitude by 50%.
- Decreased the contraction amplitude by 50%.
- Increased the contraction amplitude by 100%.
- Increased the contraction amplitude by 200%

6. The table below shows the percent change in the contraction amplitude with nerve stimulation, in normal saline and in the presence of phentolamine or atropine.

Nerve stimulation	Phentolamine + Nerve stimulation	Atropine + Nerve stimulation
+50%	+40%	+2%

What type of autonomic nerves were most likely being electrically stimulated?

- Mostly sympathetic.
- Mostly parasympathetic.
- Both sympathetic and parasympathetic in equal degree.
- I can't tell from this information.

